

**Apparent errors, omissions, and inconsistencies in:
Huihui Zhu , Wonryeol Yang, Youjin Reo, Guanhaojie Zheng , Sai Bai, Ao Liu, Yong-Young Noh,
Tin perovskite transistors and complementary circuits based on A-site cation engineering.
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V. Bruevich, and V. Podzorov,
Dept. of Physics & Astronomy, Rutgers University, 136 Frelinghuysen Rd, Piscataway, NJ 08854, USA.
E-mails: bruevich@physics.rutgers.edu, podzorov@physics.rutgers.edu

A number of apparent gross errors, omissions, and inconsistencies are found in H. Zhu *et al.*,¹ suggesting that the conclusions and claims of the paper, including the extracted values of the charge carrier mobilities, are erroneous.

- **First, there is a huge (more than 2.5 orders of magnitude) disagreement between the Hall and thin-film transistor (TFT) measurements of the (doped) charge carrier density in the perovskite films, which is likely a result of faulty Hall measurements in the van der Pauw geometry. Correspondingly, the Hall mobility claimed in this work is overestimated by more than 2.5 orders of magnitude.**
- **Second, the studied TFTs were subjected to an extreme electric biasing during the measurements, which should have resulted in enormous densities of Joule power generated in the channel, sufficient to obliterate or, at least, degrade the hybrid perovskite film and certainly enough to significantly raise its temperature, thus modifying its properties.**
- **Third, there is a more than an order of magnitude disagreement in the bulk resistivity of the same perovskite film (the “optimized” formulation) between the values obtained by different methods.**
- **Forth, strange inconsistencies are found in the TFT onset voltages.**
- **Fifth, when calculated correctly from the data presented, the actual TFT carrier mobilities turned out to be significantly lower than the claimed values.**

Details are provided below.

The Figure below is a recap of the central result of this work. It is an overlay of the original data representing the “hero” TFT device (Cs_{10%}FAPEA, Fig. 1c of H. Zhu *et al.*¹) and the same data replotted as a double-linear plot of a square-root transfer curve. The original data include a semi-log plot of the transfer curve (solid red circles) and the corresponding square-root plot for the Right-to-Left V_{GS} sweep direction (solid dark-cyan line). The replotted data obtained from the solid red circles are shown with the open circles. Note that the authors only showed the Right-to-Left V_{GS} sweep for the square-root characteristic. The overlaid symbols show both directions of the sweep, in comparison with the original single-direction curve (notice a substantial hysteresis).

The following device parameters are given in the paper:

Channel width, $W = 1000 \mu\text{m}$;

Channel length, $L = 200 \mu\text{m}$;

SiO_2 gate dielectric thickness, $d_{\text{ox}} = 100 \text{ nm}$;

The thickness of the perovskite film for the optimized (i.e., “hero”) device ($\text{Cs}_{10\%}\text{FAPEA}$, Fig. 1c), $d = 30 \text{ nm}$.

Other parameters used in the analysis:

The gate-channel capacitance per unit area corresponding to $d_{\text{ox}} = 100 \text{ nm}$, $C_i = 34.5 \text{ nF/cm}^2$;

Threshold voltage, $V_{\text{TH}} \approx 15.0 \text{ V}$ (obtained by fitting the Right-to-Left transfer curve in Fig. 1c with the standard MOSFET model (see below));

Onset voltage, $V_{\text{on}} = 16.1 \text{ V}$ (seen on the semi-log plot of the transfer curve in Fig. 1c).

A number of other important experimental parameters and conditions, relevant to the field-effect transistor (FET) and Hall effect measurements, remain undisclosed (missing from the paper), including voltage sweep rates, hysteresis in the TFT output curves, most information or the actual data on the Hall effect measurements, etc.

1. There is a huge (more than 2.5 orders of magnitude) discrepancy between the carrier densities (and, thus, mobilities) extracted from the TFT and Hall measurements.

Under the TFT biasing conditions shown in Fig. 1c of the paper (a *p*-type TFT at $V_{DS} = -40$ V), observation of a positive onset voltage indicates that the film is *p*-doped, with (preexisting) *mobile* bulk holes that need to be depleted by applying a sufficiently high positive gate voltage. This onset voltage can be easily identified on the semi-log plot (Fig. 1c): $V_{onset} = +16.1$ V. This voltage can be used to estimate the bulk carrier density of the film. Such carriers are commonly occurring in tin-based perovskites due to self-doping.² The carrier density determined (using film thickness of $d = 30$ nm) from the onset is:

$$n_{3D} = \frac{C_i \cdot V_{onset}}{e \cdot d} = 1.17 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}.$$

However, the authors stated that from the Hall measurements of the ungated same films they have extracted $n_{Hall} = 2.4 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$:

other two (Supplementary Fig. 7 shows the XPS spectra). Since the V_{sn} defects play a dominant role in deciding the hole carrier concentration of Sn perovskites⁴, Hall-effect measurements were then used to investigate the hole concentrations and Hall mobilities (μ_{Hall}) of the different perovskite thin films (Supplementary Fig. 8). The FA film shows an average hole carrier concentration of $6.5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, which decreases to $2.2 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (FAPEA) and $2.4 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for CsFAPEA films (Fig. 4b).

This shows that there is a huge (more than 2.5 orders of magnitude) inconsistency between the carrier densities obtained from the depletion point in TFTs and Hall measurements of ungated films. This disagreement cannot be explained by the differences between bulk and surface (interfacial) charge carrier transport, because both methods measure the *bulk* concentration of mobile carriers in the film. The Hall carrier density is clearly grossly underestimated, leading to a grossly overestimated Hall mobility of $\mu_{Hall} = 362 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ as reported by H. Zhu *et al.*¹

Another reason the Hall mobility reported by H. Zhu *et al.* does not make sense is that μ_{Hall} in highly disordered (semi-amorphous/polycrystalline) films, such as those studied in this work, is expected to be reduced in comparison with μ_{FET} by disorder and grain-boundary effects.³

2. Extreme biasing conditions were used in TFT measurements in this work.

The maximum power density, P_{max} , reached in the reported TFTs during the transfer curve measurements amounts to a staggering $\sim 200 \text{ W} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ (Fig. 1c in H. Zhu *et al.*¹). In FETs or TFTs, this power density is defined as the product of the source-drain voltage and the maximum source-drain current, divided by the channel area (for details, see H. H. Choi *et al.*⁴):

$$P_{max} = \frac{V_{SD} \cdot I_{SD}^{max}}{W \cdot L} \approx 200 \text{ W} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2} \text{ (for the data in Fig. 1c of H. Zhu } et al.).$$

P_{max} shows how much Joule heat is generated per unit area of the film during the measurement. To put this value in perspective, $200 \text{ W} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ is about 555 times greater than the integral power density emitted by a typical household iron operating at full power.

However, the reported Hall effect measurements do not agree with this value. Indeed, it is stated that the following Hall parameters were extracted for this film: the Hall carrier density is $n_{\text{Hall}} = 2.4 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, and the Hall mobility is $\mu_{\text{Hall}} = 362 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$:

average hole carrier concentration of $6.5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, which decreases to $2.2 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (FAPEA) and $2.4 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for CsFAPEA films (Fig. 4b). This trend is a result of the decreasing density of hole generators, V_{Sn} , agreeing well with the XPS analyses. Correspondingly, the μ_{Hall} value of the perovskite films increases from the average $\mu_{\text{Hall}} = 45 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (FA; resistivity $\rho = 2.1 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}$) to $111 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (FAPEA; $\rho = 2.5 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}$) and up to $362 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for CsFAPEA films

Thus, the Hall measurements yield the 3D resistivity of the film, $\rho_{3D} \equiv (e \cdot n_{\text{Hall}} \cdot \mu_{\text{Hall}})^{-1} = 7.2 \text{ } \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$. This simple comparison reveals a ~ 1.5 orders of magnitude mismatch (0.23 vs. $7.2 \text{ } \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$) between the resistivities of what the authors claim is the same material, the same composition, and the same type of film (the so-called “optimized” formulation). This gross inconsistency is not addressed in the paper.

The film’s bulk resistivity can also be determined from the TFT’s transfer curves at $V_{\text{GS}} = 0$ (solid red symbols in Fig. 1c of H. Zhu *et al.*¹). For the upper branch (Right-to-Left V_{GS} sweep), given the $L/W = 0.2$, $V_{\text{DS}} = -40 \text{ V}$, and $d = 30 \text{ nm}$, one obtains $\rho_{3D} = 0.9 \text{ } \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$, which is also much greater than $0.2 \text{ } \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$.

It is thus obvious that the values of ρ_{3D} are all over that place even for nominally the same sample. These strange inconsistencies either indicate poor reproducibility of the films’ properties (even for the films of nominally the same type and composition), or signal improper or dishonest disclosure of what has been actually measured and the actual measurement conditions.

4. Strange inconsistencies in the onset voltage, V_{onset}

The Figure below shows the transfer curve generated from the original Fig. 1c of H. Zhu *et al.* (solid red circles),¹ replotted on a square-root scale, with the fitting of both the linear and the saturation regimes with the Shockley FET model.⁵ Both directions of the V_{GS} sweep are shown, with the corresponding threshold voltages, V_{th} , obtained from the fits indicated. It is evident that the threshold voltages are significantly different for the two sweep directions, which might be because of the bias-stress effect or related instability.^{6,7} However, from the original semi-log plot shown in Fig. 1c, one can see that the onset voltage (indicated with the red arrow in the inset below) is *precisely* the same for both sweep directions. How can that be that the onset voltage of the “hero” device in Fig. 1c stays exactly the same on changing the sweep direction, while V_{th} is noticeably changing?

Also note that the curves presented in Fig. 1e of H. Zhu *et al.*¹ (a big bunch of curves) all exhibit a noticeable hysteresis and a clear and significant difference in the onset voltages for the two V_{GS} sweep directions. How can that be that the “hero” device (Fig. 1c) has zero difference in V_{onset} , while all other devices (Fig. 1e) seem to exhibit the expected behavior?

5. Significantly exaggerated TFT mobilities are reported in H. Zhu *et al.*¹

Even if all the inconsistencies, discrepancies and other red flags discovered here were to be ignored, and the presented TFT data were taken at face value, the proper analysis of these data reveals a number of apparent errors in the calculation of the charge carrier mobility, as detailed below. In addition, see another report on a prior paper by the same group, revealing similar issues.⁸

5.1. Because tin-based perovskite films are self-doped and conducting, the onset voltage of the resultant TFT devices is noticeably shifted to the right (Fig. 1c in H. Zhu *et al.*¹). That is why the authors had to keep the film thickness very small and apply a large positive V_{GS} to deplete the TFT channel. Under these circumstances, only a part of the transfer curve shown in Fig. 1c actually corresponds to the saturation regime, not the entire curve. Namely, the data at $-25\text{ V} < V_{GS} < 15\text{ V}$ can be fitted with the saturation regime equation, while the rest at $V_{GS} < -25\text{ V}$ is more representative of a linear regime operation of the TFT and should be fitted with the linear mobility expression. The authors have completely ignored this problem and used the saturation-regime FET equation to analyze the entire curve, which is clearly an error.

The Figure below shows the linear mobility calculated using the linear-regime part of the original transfer curve (solid red circles in the original Fig. 1c). The calculated linear mobility, averaged over the proper region, is $46.6\text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, that is, much lower than the mobility claimed in the paper. The claimed mobility of $72\text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ exceeds this value by $\sim 55\%$.

5.2. The Figure below shows the saturation mobility calculated from the original data (solid red circles in Fig. 1c). The average saturation mobility obtained in the correct region ($-25\text{ V} < V_{GS} < 15\text{ V}$) is $\mu_{sat} \approx 49.8\text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, which is again much smaller than the value reported in the paper.

6. An apparently false milestone achievement is claimed in this paper.

The above analysis shows that the mobility of the perovskite TFTs claimed in this paper (Fig. 1c) is erroneous. The authors have presented this as a milestone achievement by including a comparison with the low-temperature polysilicon (LTPS) TFTs (Fig. 1f),¹ stating that the reported perovskite TFTs outperform LTPS TFTs in terms of the mobility (the red star just above the horizontal dashed line in Fig. 1f). However, even if all the contradictions, discrepancies and inconsistencies described above were disregarded, and the presented TFT data were accepted as true experimental data, the correctly calculated mobility from those data would be at best $\mu \sim 46 - 50 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ (a green star added on the original Fig. 1f below), which is significantly lower than μ of LTPS TFTs. This shows that the claim of a milestone achievement is erroneous.

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